

THE NEUROSCIENCE

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ABSTRACT:

Neuroscience is the part of science that describes the study of the central nervous system such as its structures, functions, molecular mechanisms, physiological aspects, and understanding diseases of the nervous system. It is often confused with Neurology, which, in turn, is a specialized area of medicine concerned with the study of disorders and diseases of the nervous system, which involves the diagnosis and treatment of pathological conditions of the central, peripheral, and autonomic nervous systems.

Keywords: neuroscience, psychology, health

Neuroscience is usually studied by many different professionals, not only by neurologists. Among the professionals who are interested in neuroscience are pharmacists, physical therapists, nurses, physicians, nutritionists, biologists, biomedical and even engineers, because the training in this area can elucidate the new robotic architecture techniques based on neuroscience.

This science can be divided into five major groups: molecular, cellular, systemic, behavioral, and cognitive neuroscience.

Molecular neuroscience, neurochemistry, or molecular neurobiology - the branch of neuroscience responsible for the study of molecules that have functional importance and their possible interactions in the nervous system;

Cellular neuroscience, neurocytology or cellular neurobiology - this area studies the cells that make up the nervous system, their structures and functions;

Systemic neuroscience, neurophysiology, neurohistology or neuroanatomy- studies the possible connections between the nerves of the brain (called pathways) and different peripheral regions. The cell groups located in these pathways are also considered;

Behavioral neuroscience, psychobiology or psychophysiology - studies the structures that are related to behavior or phenomena such as anxiety, depression, sleep among other behaviors;

Cognitive neuroscience or neuropsychology - deals with all mental capacities related to intelligence such as language, memory, self-awareness, perception, attention, learning, among others.

Like all major areas, neuroscience had great scientists who changed the course of humanity and medicine with their discoveries, among them those who received Nobel Prizes in physiology or medicine;

1906 - Golgi was awarded the prize for studies on the structure of the nervous system, this was shared with Ramon y Cajal who also proposed the way axons grow and that neural cells could be involved in the detection of chemical signals.

Another Nobel Prize winner was Charles Scott Sherrington who explained about the reflex arc and flexion-extension of muscles by proving that the excitation of one muscle group was inversely proportional to that of the opposite muscle group.

In 1952 Alan Hodkin published his and Andrew Huxley's theory based on the action potential of nerves, where electrical impulses sent by nerve cells were able to control the activity of the organism, and in 1963 he received the Nobel Prize with Huxley and John Eccles for their description of synapses, and also suggested the hypothesis of ion channels, which was confirmed years later.

Among the current Nobel Prize winning neuroscientists are; Kandel, Greengard and Carlsson, winners of the 2000 prize, who revealed the essential aspects in the process of memory formation.

Among Brazilians working in neurosciences is Miguel Nicolelis, named in 2009 as one of the most influential Brazilians, and the first Brazilian scientist to receive an award from the U.S. National Institutes of Health. Nicolelis was one of the creators of the exoskeleton project that made it possible for a disabled person to kick off the 2014 World Cup in Brazil.

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